

GAUSS USULI BILAN NORMAL TENGLASHTIRISH SISTEMASIDA YECHISH. PARAMETRIK USULDA TENGLASHTIRISH BAJARISH KETMA-KETLIGI

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6390826>

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada Gauss usuli yordamida normal tenglamalar sistemasini yechish tadbirlari, tanlab olingan parametrlarga tuzatmalar kiritish, kerakli bo'lgan parametrik tenglamalarni tanlab olish va tenglamasini tuzish.

Kalit so'zlar: Gauss usuli, parametr, kerakli va ortiqcha o'lchovlar, sistema, normal tenglama, matritsa, funksiya, Kramer va boshqalar.

I. Barcha o'lchashlar n , kerakli o'lchashlar k va ortiqcha o'lchashlar r soninini aniqlash.

II. Soni kerakli o'lchashlar k ga teng va bir-biri bilan bog'liq bo'lmagan, ya'ni har qanday parameter boshqasi orqali ifodalanmaydigan shartlarni qanoatlantirgan holda T_1, \dots, T_k parametrlarni tanlash. Bunda $T_i = f_i(T_1, T_2, \dots, T_{j-1}, T_{j+1}, \dots, T_k)$ funksiya sodir bo'lmasligi kerak.

III. $X_i = f_i(T_1, \dots, T_k)$ ($i=1, 2, \dots, n$) - parametrik tenglamalar bog'liqligini tuzish.

$$x_i + v_i = f_i(t_1, \dots, t_k)$$

IV. Tuzatmalarning parametrik tenglamasini tuzish

$$v_i = a_{i1}\tau_1 + a_{i2}\tau_2 + \dots + a_{ik}\tau_k + l_i \quad (i=1, \dots, n)$$

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$$V = A \times \Delta X + L$$

V. Tuzatmalar normal tenglamalarini tuzish

$$[pa_1 a_1] \tau_1 + [pa_1 a_2] \tau_2 + \dots + [pa_1 a_k] \tau_k + [pa_1 l] = 0$$

$$[pa_2 a_1] \tau_1 + [pa_2 a_2] \tau_2 + \dots + [pa_2 a_k] \tau_k + [pa_2 l] = 0$$

.....

$$[pa_k a_1] \tau_1 + [pa_k a_2] \tau_2 + \dots + [pa_k a_k] \tau_k + [pa_k l] = 0$$

yoki, matritsa ko'rinishida

$$R \times \Delta X + A^T L = 0$$

bu yerda, $R = A \times A^T$ - normal tenglamalar koeffitsiyentlar matritsasi.

VI. Tuzatmalarning normal tenglamalar sistemasini yechish. Bunga masalani matematikadagi nomalumlarni ketma-ket yo'qotishga asoslangan: Xoletskiy,

kvadrat ildizlar, Jordan, Gauss, Kramer va boshqa yechish usullaridan foydalanish mumkin. Masalan, Gaussda 3 noma'lumli 3 chiziqli aniqlangan tenglamalar sistemasini yechimidan kerakli noma'lumlarning taxminiy qiymatiga τ_v tuzatma olinadi:

$$[a_1a_1] \tau_1 + [a_1a_2] \tau_2 + [a_1a_3] \tau_3 + [a_1l] = 0$$

$$[a_1a_2] \tau_1 + [a_2a_2] \tau_2 + [a_2a_3] \tau_3 + [a_2l] = 0$$

$$[a_1a_3] \tau_1 + [a_2a_3] \tau_2 + [a_3a_3] \tau_3 + [a_3l] = 0$$

$$[a_1a_1] \tau_1 + [a_1a_2] \tau_2 + [a_1a_3] \tau_3 + [a_1l] = 0$$

$$\dots\dots\dots [a_2a_2] \tau_2 + [a_2a_3] \tau_3 + [a_2l] = 0$$

$$\dots\dots\dots [a_3a_3] \tau_3 + [a_3l] = 0$$

$$\tau_3 = \frac{[a_3l*2]}{[a_3a_3*2]}$$

$$\tau_2 = \frac{[a_3a_3*1]}{[a_2a_2*1]} \tau_3 - \frac{[a_2l*1]}{[a_2a_2*1]}$$

$$\tau_1 = \frac{[a_1a_2]}{[a_1a_1]} \tau_2 - \frac{[a_1a_3]}{[a_1a_1]} \tau_3 - \frac{[a_2l]}{[a_1a_1]}$$

Uning matritsa ko'rinishi

$$\Delta X = -R^{-1} \times A^T L = 0$$

VII. O'lchash natijalariga tuzatmalar hisoblash

$$v_i = a_{i1}\tau_1 + a_{i2}\tau_2 + \dots + a_{ik}\tau_k + l_i \quad (i=1, \dots, n)$$

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$$V = A \times \Delta X + L$$

VIII. O'lchangan kattaliklarning $x_i = x_i + v_i$ va parametrlarning $t_v = t_v^0 + \tau_v$ tenglashtirilgan qiymatlari topiladi.

1-chizma

1-jadval

Burchaklar №	Burchaklar	O'lchangan qiymatlar "x, "
1.	AOB	58° 15' 41,8"
2.	BOC	38 10 06.8
3.	COD	61 01 07.0
4.	AOC	96 25 45.1
5.	BOD	99 11 13.3
6.	AOD	157 26 52.6

Yechish.

I. Kerakli va ortiqcha o'lchashlar soninini hisoblaymiz. Barcha o'lchashlar $n=6$, kerakli o'lchashlar $k=3$ va ortiqcha o'lchashlar $r=n-k=6-3=3$ ga teng bo'ladi.

II. Soni kerakli o'lchashlar $k=3$ ga teng va bir-biri bilan bog'liq bo'lmagan, ya'ni har qanday parameter boshqasi orqali ifodalanmaydigan shartlarni qanoatlantirgan holda parametrlarni tanlaymiz. Bunda $T_i = f_i (T_1, T_2, \dots, T_{j-1}, T_{j+1}, \dots, T_k)$ funksiya sodir bo'lmashligi kerak. Bu shartlarni boshlang'ich uchta burchak qanoatlantiradi. Va ularni parametrlar sifatida qabul qilamiz $T_1 = X_1; T_2 = X_2; T_3 = X_3$; Ularning tenglashtirilgan qiymati sifatida t_1, t_2 va t_3 larni olamiz.

III. $X_i = f_i (T_1, \dots, T_k)$ ($i=1, 2, \dots, n$) - parametrik tenglamalar bog'liqligini tuzish.

Hamma oltita o'lchangan miqdorlar tenglashtirilgan qiymatini uchta kerakli noma'lumlarning tenglashtirilgan qiymati orqali ifodalaymiz:

$$x_i = x_1 + v_i = f_i (t_1, t_2, t_3)$$

Ko'rilayotgan misolimiz uchun tenglamalar bog'liqligi

- | | |
|-----------------|-----------------------------|
| 1) $x'_1 = t_1$ | 4) $x'_4 = t_1 + t_2$ |
| 2) $x'_2 = t_2$ | 5) $x'_5 = t_2 + t_3$ |
| 3) $x'_3 = t_3$ | 6) $x'_6 = t_1 + t_2 + t_3$ |

III¹ . Parametrlarning taxminiy qiymatlarini hisoblash. Ma'lumki parametrlar birinchi uchta o'lchash natijalariga teng, parametrlarning taxminiy qiymatlari sifatida burchaklarning o'lchash natijalarini olamiz, $t_1 = t_1^0 + \tau_1; \dots; t_k = t_k^0 + \tau_n$

$$t_1 = t_1^0 + \tau_1 \quad t_2 = t_2^0 + \tau_2 \quad t_3 = t_3^0 + \tau_3$$

bu yerda,

$$t_1^0 = x_1 = 58^{\circ}15'41,8^n \quad t_2^0 = x_2 = 38^{\circ}10'06,8^n \quad t_3^0 = x_3 = 61^{\circ}01'07,0^n$$

IV. Tuzatmalarning parametrik tenglamasini tuzish.

Umumiy holda $x' = x_1 + v_i$ va $a_{i1}\tau_1 + a_{i2}\tau_2 + \dots + a_{ik}\tau_k + l_i$ larga asosan biz ko'rayotgan masala uchun tuzatmalarning parametric tenglamasi quyidagicha bo'ladi:

$$a_{i1}\tau_1 + a_{i2}\tau_2 + \dots + a_{ik}\tau_k + l_i \quad i=1, 2, \dots, 6$$

bu yerda:

$$a_{i1} = \left(\frac{\partial x'_1}{\partial t_1}\right)_0 \quad a_{i2} = \left(\frac{\partial x'_1}{\partial t_2}\right)_0 \quad a_{i3} = \left(\frac{\partial x'_1}{\partial t_3}\right)_0$$

$$l_i = f_i (t_1^0, t_2^0, t_3^0) - x_i = x_1^0 - x_1$$

Tuzatmalarning parametric tenglamasi koeffitsientlarini va ozod xadlarini har bir tenglamalar bog'liqligi uchun yozamiz.

1-chi tenglamalar bog'liqligi uchun:

$$a_{11} = \left(\frac{\partial x_1}{\partial t_1}\right)_0 + 1 \quad a_{12} = \left(\frac{\partial x_1}{\partial t_2}\right)_0 = 0 \quad a_{13} = \left(\frac{\partial x_1}{\partial t_3}\right)_0 = 0$$

$$l_1 = t_1^0 - x_1 = x_1^0 - x_1 = 58^{\circ}15'41,8^n - 58^{\circ}15'41,8^n = 0$$

2-chi tenglamalar bog'liqligi uchun:

$$a_{21} = \left(\frac{\partial x_2}{\partial t_1}\right)_0 = 0 \quad a_{22} = \left(\frac{\partial x_2}{\partial t_2}\right)_0 + 1 \quad a_{23} = \left(\frac{\partial x_2}{\partial t_3}\right)_0 = 0$$

$$l_2 = x_1^0 - x_1 = 38^0 10' 06.8^n - 38^0 10' 06.8^n = 0$$

3-chi tenglamalar bog'liqligi uchun:

$$a_{31} = \left(\frac{\partial x_3}{\partial t_1}\right)_0 = 0 \quad a_{32} = \left(\frac{\partial x_3}{\partial t_2}\right)_0 = 0 \quad a_{33} = \left(\frac{\partial x_3}{\partial t_3}\right)_0 + 1$$

$$l_3 = x_1^0 - x_1 = 61^0 01' 07.0^n - 61^0 01' 07.0^n = 0$$

4-chi tenglamalar bog'liqligi uchun:

$$a_{41} = \left(\frac{\partial x_4}{\partial t_1}\right)_0 + 1 \quad a_{42} = \left(\frac{\partial x_4}{\partial t_2}\right)_0 + 1 \quad a_{43} = \left(\frac{\partial x_4}{\partial t_3}\right)_0 = 0$$

$$l_4 = x_1^0 - x_1 = (t_1^0 + t_2^0) - x_4 = (58^0 15' 41.8^n + 38^0 10' 06.8^n) - 96^0 25' 45.1^n = + 3.5''$$

5-chi tenglamalar bog'liqligi uchun:

$$a_{51} = \left(\frac{\partial x_5}{\partial t_1}\right)_0 = 0 \quad a_{52} = \left(\frac{\partial x_5}{\partial t_2}\right)_0 + 1 \quad a_{53} = \left(\frac{\partial x_5}{\partial t_3}\right)_0 = 0$$

$$l_5 = (t_2^0 + t_3^0) - x_5 = (58^0 15' 41.8^n + 38^0 10' 06.8^n) - 96^0 25' 45.1^n = + 0.5''$$

6-chi tenglamalar bog'liqligi uchun:

$$a_{61} = \left(\frac{\partial x_6}{\partial t_1}\right)_0 + 1 \quad a_{62} = \left(\frac{\partial x_6}{\partial t_2}\right)_0 + 1 \quad a_{63} = \left(\frac{\partial x_6}{\partial t_3}\right)_0 + 1$$

$$l_6 = (t_1^0 + t_2^0 + t_3^0) - x_6 = (58^0 15' 41.8^n + 38^0 10' 06.8^n + 61^0 01' 07.0^n) - 58^0 15' 41.8^n = + 3.0''$$

Tuzatmalar tenglamalari koeffitsiyentlari matrisasi quyidagi ko'rinishda bo'ladi

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} 1.0.0 \\ 0.1.0 \\ 0.0.1 \\ 1.1.0 \\ 0.1.1 \\ 1.1.1 \end{pmatrix}$$

Hamma o'lchashlar uchun tuzatmalar tenglamasini yozamiz:

$$v_1 = a_{11}\tau_1 + a_{12}\tau_2 + a_{13}\tau_k + l_1 = + 1*\tau_1 + 0*\tau_2 + 0\tau_3 + 0 = \tau_1 \text{ ga ko'ra}$$

$$v_1 = \tau_1$$

bo'ladi, qolganlari ham shu tartibda yoziladi.

$$2) v_2 = \tau_2$$

$$3) v_3 = \tau_3$$

$$4) v_4 = \tau_1 + \tau_2 + 3.5''$$

$$5) v_5 = \tau_2 + \tau_3 + 0.5''$$

$$6) v_6 = \tau_1 + \tau_2 + \tau_3 + 3.0''$$

Ko'rilayotgan masala uchun k=3 nomalumli k chiziqli normal tenglamalar sistemasiga ko'ra tuzatmalar tenglamasi koeffitsientlarini 2-jadvalga mos ravishda yozamiz.

2-jadval

Tenglamalar	a_1	a_2	a_3	l (sek)	s	V'	$V' * V'$
1	+1				+1	-1.5'	2.25
2		+1			+1	-1.0'	1.00
3			+1		+1	0.0	0.00
4	+1	+1		+3.5	+5.5	+1.0'	1.00
5		+1	+1	+0.5	+2.5	-0.5'	0.25
6	+1	+1	+1	+3.0	+6.0	+0.5'	0.25
\sum	$[a_1]=+3$	$[a_2]=+4$	$[a_3]=+3$	$[l]=+7$	$[s]=+17$	$[V]$	$[V * V]=$
Noma'lumlar	τ_1	τ_2	τ_3				$= 4.75$
	$a_1]$	$a_2]$	$a_3]$	$l]$	$s]$		
$[a_{1i}]$	$[a_1 a_1]$ +3	$[a_1 a_2]$ +2	$[a_1 a_3]$ +1	$[a_1 l]$ +6.5	$[a_1 s]$ +12.5		
$[a_{2i}]$		$[a_2 a_2]$ +4	$[a_2 a_3]$ +2	$[a_2 l]$ +7.0	$[a_2 s]$ +15.0		
$[a_{3i}]$			$[a_3 a_3]$ +3	$[a_3 l]$ +3.5	$[a_3 s]$ +9.5		
$[l]$				$[l * l]$ +21.5	$[l * s]$ +38.5		
$[s]$					$[s * s]$ +75.5		

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